

Chad Situation Report

At the heart of Chad's longstanding crisis lie a series of unaddressed democratisation challenges that have been recently exacerbated by chronic regional instability. That includes the killing of the longtime president of Chad by armed resistance that situated in the border of Libya just after become announced the winner of election April, 2021. The short overview of the country's political history has amply demonstrated some fundamental aspects of Chadian political life. Decades of political unrest, regularly alternating with full-scale civil war have left significant traces on the country's political and state institutions.^[1]

One of the most important features of Chadian political and social life is the permanence of violence as a means of expressing different interests. It is a political culture in a country that has never experienced a constitutional regime change since its independence. Apart from the first president of the country, all Heads of State have seized power by violent means. In this context, rebels and other warlords are actually political entrepreneurs who make use of the only available tool (armed rebellion) to gain power either by conquering the central authority in the capital or through tactical 'power-sharing' with the regime. This has led to a high interchangeability of political actors according to which today's warlords can be considered the ruling elite of tomorrow and vice-versa. To seize and maintain power, political entrepreneurs are therefore dependant on their capacities to build alliances that are by definition fragile and ever shifting. The predominance of violence in the political culture is also deeply rooted in the country's social fabric, where the possession of a weapon (be it as soldier, policeman, customs agent or even bandit) generally provides a high social status. This is fuelled by a widespread culture of factionalism that, far more than ethnicity, explains the shifting power configurations in Chad.^[2]

The so-called democratisation process of the 1990s barely changed the modalities of Chadian political life. On the contrary, it provided the ruling elite with the necessary legal means to legitimise the violent exercise of political power. When Idriss Deby seized power in 1990 by ending the dictatorship of Hissein Habre, he raised the hope that Chad would break with its long tradition of politico-military rule. His first steps towards opening up the political system were rather promising in a country deeply traumatised by the tyranny of his predecessor,

with which Deby was also prominently associated as a former Chief of Staff. He reintroduced a multi-party system, authorised the emergence of pluralist media and allowed for the adoption of a new democratic constitution in 1996. However, the first presidential (1996) and legislative elections (1997) rapidly indicated that the ruling party and its leader were still caught in the logic of the one-party system. This impression was confirmed in the second set of elections (2001 and 2002) that proved even more chaotic in terms of organisation and popular participation and which led to its boycotting by the main political parties. In reaction to the mostly negative statements about his re-election, Deby made the promise to abide by the constitution and to step down in 2006.

The direct trigger of the current political crisis in Chad is to be found in Deby's decision in 2004 to amend the constitution and run for a third term. This has not only alienated important parts of his inner circle and ethnic group, who reproached him for monopolising the country's resources for his own clan's benefit but also radicalised the already existing tendency towards the militarisation of political entrepreneurs. In the absence of democratic institutions to manage elite competition, armed rebellion remains the only way to express political grievances. As soon as he announced his will to run for a third term, Deby antagonised large factions of his close entourage, with some of them joining the rebellion. In fact, two of the main rebel movements in Chad are currently led by former close collaborators of President Deby, who changed sides and thereby confirmed the thin line between government and rebellion.[3] The defection of these two leaders was just the most visible point of a much greater number of defections that significantly affected Deby's legitimacy. Although rebel movements are known for their incapacity to form sustainable political platforms, they generally manage to build ad-hoc coalitions aimed at seizing power. In that respect, the February 2008 coup attempt was almost identical with another similar coup in 2006 that also failed because of decisive French involvement on Deby's side, the only difference being that the April 2006 coup attempt was organised by another coalition of rebel movements led by Mahamat Nour –not to be confused with Mahamat Nouri– who subsequently became Defence Minister in the Government after Libyan-led negotiations.

To summarise, it can be argued that the concentration of power in Deby's hands, increased corruption, the militarisation of his regime and the systematic repression of opposition

leaders do constitute a serious threat to sustainable peace in Chad. But most worrying of all is the President's adamant refusal to find a negotiated political solution to the country's problems through negotiations with both civilian parties and rebel movements. Deby's strategy has always consisted in signing separate agreements with civilian opposition groups and armed movements. By doing so he seeks to avoid the creation of a platform of all opposition groups against him. Part of this attitude is due to the strong support the President receives from important international actors. The outcome is that he is sowing the seeds of the further institutionalisation of coups as a political instrument in his country.

The overall electoral fraud in Chad started from the president which was elected to a five-year term. President Idriss Déby Itno took power in 1990 during a rebellion, and then overwhelmingly won elections in 1996, 2001, 2006, and 2011. In the 2016 poll, he received just under 60 percent of the vote, defeating opposition leader Saleh Kebzabo, who took 13 percent. The opposition rejected the result, citing electoral irregularities. The Independent National Electoral Commission (CENI) announced that the next presidential on April 2021 was President Idriss but he just killed by armed resistance just after week.

The position of prime minister was abolished by the 2018 constitution. In December 2020, legislators approved constitutional amendments allowing the president to appoint a vice president, among other provisions. The amendments were promulgated by Déby later that month.^[3]

The unicameral National Assembly currently consists of 188 members elected to four-year terms. The ruling political party, Déby's Patriotic Salvation Movement (MPS), and allied parties control 117 seats. Elections have not been organized since 2011, with legislative elections due in 2015 having been repeatedly postponed. In July 2020, CENI announced another delay, this time to October 2021.

Constitutional reforms promulgated in December 2020 provide for the creation of an indirectly elected Senate, with members serving staggered six-year terms. No senators were seated at year's end, with its envisioned powers remaining with the lower house.

The CENI's leadership is appointed by the country's entrenched political class through the National Framework for Political Dialogue (CNDP), and civil society is excluded from the process. In 2019, the CNDP adopted a revised electoral code that will reduce the number of lower-house members from 188 to 161 in the next legislature, over the objection of opposition members.

In December 2020, the National Assembly—whose mandate had long expired—approved constitutional reforms that, among other changes, reduced the age of eligibility for presidential candidates to from 45 years to 40. Opposition politicians denounced the adoption of the reform package by a legislative body with expired mandates and the lack of a popular referendum on the proposals.

There are more than 130 registered political parties in Chad, though most of them are aligned with the ruling party. The MPS enjoys significant influence, and has held a majority in the National Assembly since 1997.

Opposition parties are subject to government harassment. For several days in late October and early November 2020, after opposition politicians and civil society members criticized a government-led forum on political reform, the headquarters of several parties and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) were surrounded by police.^[4]

The mandate of the current legislature expired in 2015 and elections have been repeatedly postponed, leaving the opposition no avenue to increase support or gain power through elections. The political opposition is legally recognized, but opposition leaders who publicly criticize the government risk harassment and arrest. Opposition leaders have disappeared after entering state custody.

Extensive kinship networks tied to the president and his family have resulted in a concentration of political and economic power. The government is not accountable to voters in practice, and voters have few effective means of influencing or participating in politics.

The military also wields considerable influence, and President Déby has closely affiliated himself with the armed forces to hold political power. In August 2020, as Chad celebrated 60

years of independence from France, the MPS-controlled legislature awarded Déby the title of marshal.

Members of the Beri ethnic group control Chad's political, economic, and military spheres, causing resentment among the country's other ethnic groups. Christians in the south are largely excluded from political power; some Christians hold government positions, but their voice is limited. Cabinet members and some officials were previously required to be sworn in on a Bible or Quran, but that requirement was eliminated by constitutional amendments promulgated in December 2020.

Women hold few senior positions in government and political parties and are largely excluded from local governance bodies in rural areas. LGBT+ people are severely marginalized, impacting their ability to engage in political processes and advocate for their interests.^[5]

Briefing Note about Chad

Political instability in the Central African country has deep roots in the past due to its French colonisation, the long tradition of violence between different ethnic groups, the lack of natural resources and the weaknesses of institutions. Political leaders have resorted to repression and authoritarian rule to consolidate successive governments but personal rivalries and ideological and ethnic differences have prevented the country's governance. Power has shifted from Southern political and economic domination in post-independence Chad to Northern supremacy after Deby's successful coup in 1990. Violence is deeply rooted in the country's political culture and in the widespread factionalism that, far more than ethnicity, explains the shifting power configurations in Chad. Power is seized by violent means and the balance of power is contingent on the armed pressure of rebels and other warlords because armed rebellion remains the only way to express political grievances in the absence of democratic institutions.

The current political crisis in Chad was triggered by the killing of President Deby's and the announcement of translational government lead by his son which is not legitimate according to the constitution. His son will allow him to postpone democratic reforms without

negotiating a political solution to the country's problems with civilian parties. As regards the rebel movements, His son like his father still believes he will be able to fight them thanks to the procurement of military equipment with oil revenues of oil and by accusing them of being terrorist organizations in order to gain foreign military support including France. The key threats to a sustainable peace in Chad are the concentration of power in the hands of Deby's family and ethnic hands, the increased corruption and militarization of his regime and the systematic repression of opposition leaders.

Recommendations for reforms

Below are some of our recommendation includes in the next 1 year translation period includes

1. Change the Tailoring of electoral regulation, to de-enfranchise candidates or groups of people by have new electoral regulation that includes all stake holders.
2. Make possible of system that does not favor Ethnic-cultural and religious manipulations of the selection process.
3. Improve the campaigns and legal frame work to protect using the apparatus of state media, logistics, personnel in favor of the incumbent, particularly at re-election periods.
4. Make the translational government inclusive and the judiciary system independent so that Intimidation harassment of voters by things and police to discourage people from exercising their voting rights not to be happened as it was before.
5. Make possible the real independent election commission to prevent monetization of the electoral procedure before selection of candidates at party and electoral commission level.

Reference List

1. Elcano, C. F. R. I. (2008, June 6). *Inicio*. Fundación Real Instituto Elcano. http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/wps/portal/riecano_en/contenido?WCM_GLOBAL_CONTEXT=/elcano/elcano_in/zonas_in/sub-saharan+africa/ari59-2008
2. Freedom House. (n.d.). Chad. Retrieved April 28, 2021, from <https://freedomhouse.org/country/chad/freedom-world/2021>

Recommendation for Chad In the Next 1 Year of Translational Period Regarding Improving the Electoral Process

3. Chad-Conflict-Insights-vol-1. (n.d.). ReliefWeb. Retrieved April 28, 2021, from <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Chad-Conflict-Insights-vol-1-23042021.pdf>
4. Guide-to-risk-factors-for-elections-g5-sahel-external. (n.d.). IDEA. Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.idea.int/sites/default/files/publications/guide-to-risk-factors-for-elections-g5-sahel-external.pdf>
5. Chad: Pre-Election Crackdown on Opponents. (2021, April 8). Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2021/04/08/chad-pre-election-crackdown-opponents>

Reading Material

- **Electoral Cycle**
<http://ecycle.idea.int/>, under ‘select purposes’ menu, choose ‘electoral malpractice’, under ‘select actors’ menu, choose any actor. You will notice a number of potential areas of electoral manipulation will appear, linked to various stages in the election cycle.
- **Freedom House Country report for 2016**
<https://freedomhouse.org/report/freedom-world/freedom-world-2016>
- **Report Checkbook Elections** (introduction and conclusion)
http://carnegieendowment.org/files/Checkbook_Elections_brief.pdf
- **Ace Project’s ‘Considerations when assessing campaign finance regulation’**
<https://aceproject.org/ace-en/focus/campaign-finance/considerations-when-assessing-campaign-finance>
- **ACE Election Observation Portal** (election observation reports)
<http://aceproject.org/dop>
- **World Values Survey** (Public Perceptions)
Online data analysis tool (<http://www.worldvaluessurvey.org/WVSOnline.jsp>).
- **Perceptions of Electoral Integrity Index** (Expert Perceptions)
Year in Elections, mid-2016 report
(<https://www.dropbox.com/s/db5i4sct9xdnv3l/THE%20YEAR%20IN%20ELECTIONS%20UPDATE%20>